

CONSTELLATIONS: A NEW PARADIGM FOR EARTH OBSERVATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The last decade has seen a significant increase in the number and the capabilities of remote sensing satellites launched by the international community. A relatively new approach is the launching of heterogeneous satellites to form constellations. Constellations provide scientists a capability to acquire science data, not only from specific instruments on a single satellite, but also from instruments on other satellites that fly in close proximity. Constellation design is driven primarily by science requirements. Scientists from each member satellite choose the orbit that enables their science and concurrent observations with the other satellites. Although the satellites are controlled by different organizations around the world, the teams cooperate and coordinate operations to ensure safety. This paper presents the benefits of joining an on-orbit constellation and ideas for the long-term evolution of constellations.

Index Terms— A-Train, Constellation, remote sensing, Earth observations

1. INTRODUCTION

A relatively new approach for performing satellite earth observations has been the launching of satellites into heterogeneous constellations. The first significant earth observing constellation began with the launch of the United States Geological Survey's (USGS's) Landsat-7 and NASA's Earth Observing System (EOS) Terra satellites in 1999 into a 705 kilometer altitude, sun-synchronous orbit. The Project Scientists for Terra and Landsat-7 signed a pre-launch agreement to do constellation flying. These were joined the following year by the Earth Observing-1 (EO-1) satellite from NASA and the Satellite de Aplicaciones Cientificas-C (SAC-C) satellite from the Argentine Commission on Space Activities (CONAE), resulting in a full-fledged orbiting constellation. The 4 satellites cross the equator within minutes of each other at the mean local time (MLT) range of 10:00 a.m. - 10:30 a.m. Hence, the group is known as the "Morning Constellation" (Fig. 1).

In 2002, a second constellation began forming with the launch of NASA's EOS Aqua satellite, followed 2 years later by EOS Aura. A third satellite, Polarization and

Figure 1 – Earth Observing Constellations

Anisotropy of Reflectances for Atmospheric Sciences Coupled with Observations from Lidar (PARASOL), managed by the French Space Agency, Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales (CNES), joined the A-Train in 2004. This was followed by the Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observations (CALIPSO) satellite (a joint U.S./French mission) and CloudSat (a joint NASA/Canadian Space Agency (CSA)/U.S. Air Force mission) in 2006. The sixth satellite, the Orbiting Carbon Observatory, was unsuccessfully launched in February 2009. Another NASA mission, Glory, is scheduled to join in 2010, bringing the total to 6 satellites and 15 instruments providing near-coincident science data. JAXA's Global Change Observation Mission-W1 (GCOM-W1) recently agreed to join (launch planned for 2012).

All these missions fly in 705 kilometer altitude, sun-synchronous orbits like the Morning Constellation, but cross the equator at an MLT range of 1:30 p.m. – 2:00 p.m., so this constellation is known as the "Afternoon Constellation". This paper focuses on the Afternoon Constellation, which is often referred to by its more popular name, the "A-Train".

2. CONSTELLATION ADVANTAGES

In principle, a constellation forms a single "virtual" platform which enables coincident observations across the actual platforms, thus enabling more comprehensive measurements and providing better science. Constellations provide the

scientists a capability to acquire science data, not only from specific instruments on a single satellite, but also from instruments on other satellites that fly in close proximity. Initial results from the A-Train (especially following the CALIPSO/CloudSat launch) attest to the tremendous scientific value of constellation flying.

In its most basic usage, the co-located data for constellations can provide context for non-imaging active instruments. In addition, new merged data products become possible. For example, in the A-Train, CloudSat’s Cloud Profiling Radar (CPR) instrument can penetrate deep into the cloud layer, while CALIPSO’s lidar instrument measures the fine structural detail above and between the clouds. Together these instruments sample profiles of our global atmosphere more completely than either could individually. Furthermore, combining these two data sets with those from Aura’s Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS) instrument provides an unprecedented opportunity to study fast, small-scale cloud processes (Fig. 2). Additional MLS measurements (e.g., of CO and H₂O) are then used to better understand cloud formation/evolution and their interactions with the environment in the upper atmosphere [1]. Recognizing the enhancements provided by these merged data sets, and at the request of the Aura Project Scientist, Aura was moved up much closer to CloudSat in May 2008 to improve the overlap of the MLS - CloudSat observations.

Figure 2 – MLS-CloudSat Concurrent Science
(Source: Dr. D. L. Wu, California Institute of Technology)

Another advantage of constellation flying is the risk reduction it provides to the overall observing system approach. With all observations concentrated to a single platform, a failed launch or a system failure in that platform would lead to loss of all observations, whereas the same type of failure in a single constellation satellite will not impact the other constellation missions. Constellations also allow for more focused, less complex satellites. This shortens the time from concept to on-orbit operations and enables allocating the costs for all the missions over several years. It also enables an evolutionary approach to the

overall constellation’s measurement capabilities, allowing the measurement resolution and character to change as science needs and instrument capabilities evolve.

3. CONSTELLATION MISSION DESIGN

First and foremost, constellation mission design is driven by science requirements. Individually, each mission performs important science measurements which fully justify the individual mission’s flight. However, when combined with observations from the other partner missions and instruments, the derived data products can significantly add to the overall science return of all missions involved. The additional investment from the instrument and mission teams in the constellation is not in hardware development, but in collaboration and coordination.

Constellation flying presents challenges that must be addressed in order to achieve the desired science results. Planners need to ensure not only that satellites in a constellation operate safely together, but also how multiple satellites can fly in close proximity without interfering with each other when commands are uplinked or data are downlinked to their respective ground stations. Radio frequency interference (RFI) is minimized by frequency selection and diverse ground station resources.

Propellant is also an important consideration. The satellite must carry enough fuel to follow orbital changes of the constellation “lead satellite”, for example, to conduct periodic inclination adjust maneuvers to maintain a target orbit MLT. Also, there must be enough fuel to be able to exit the constellation and decommission the satellite at the end of life to meet agency guidelines for limiting orbital debris. In addition, one specific A-Train lesson learned is that constellation satellites should have a retrograde maneuver capability to ensure maximum flexibility in dealing with on-orbit anomalies.

Some constellations, such as the A-Train, present additional operational challenges resulting from the broad geographical distribution of its ground systems and science personnel (Fig. 3), requiring coordination across different schedules, time zones, and cultures.

Figure 3– A-Train Science and Operations Centers

4. BUILDING A CONSTELLATION

Unlike constellations composed of similar satellites operated for a specific purpose, such as the Global Positioning System (GPS), the A-Train consists of several diverse satellites, each with its own science objectives.

Flying in a constellation was not the primary objective of the Aqua mission prior to launch, although careful planning was done to ensure proper phasing with the Terra satellite so as to avoid data downlink schedule conflicts at the ground stations. After Aqua's launch in 2002, other missions wanted to leverage on the capabilities of Aqua and Aura by flying close to them. In response, NASA formed the Afternoon Constellation Mission Operations Working Group (MOWG) in 2003 to establish (through negotiation) a set of guidelines for, and agreements between all mission teams. Through the MOWG, all the mission teams cooperate and coordinate their operations to ensure that the A-Train will be operated safely and effectively [2] [3].

These A-Train guidelines and agreements can be applied to other constellations and are summarized below.

4.1 Safety

Mission safety is a primary concern. The A-Train satellites, for example, all fly within seconds to minutes of each other. A process was established to facilitate coordination among the mission teams to ensure orbital safety, while allowing the teams to maintain autonomy over their missions. Procedures and systems were put in place to avoid unplanned close approaches between A-Train satellites or with orbital debris:

- A centralized constellation coordination system was developed to monitor the locations and planned movements of the A-Train satellites and ensure that potentially dangerous deviations would be detected and announced expeditiously.
- Contingency procedures that define each mission team's response or action plan to mitigate an on-orbit anomaly were agreed upon and documented.
- An orbital debris monitoring task was instituted so that any satellite in jeopardy of conjunction with orbital debris is notified early enough to be able to plan and perform a debris avoidance maneuver.

4.2 Minimal Coordination of Mission Operations

Constellation operations must not place an undue operational burden on the mission teams. The teams are busy enough with their mission-specific tasks without adding tasks to support the constellation. The A-Train MOWG agreed on a *control box* philosophy whereby each satellite is assigned its own slot in space (Fig. 4). As long as a mission team keeps its satellite within its assigned space, coordination with the other teams is minimal. The centralized coordination system confirms each satellite's

position within its control box using each mission's daily predicted ephemeris, which is shared among all members.

Figure 4— Orbital Configuration of Control Boxes

Occasionally, constellation teams must coordinate their activities to manage complex operations. For example, inclination adjust maneuvers are executed periodically to maintain the required MLT. Each mission carries different constraints and concerns regarding the frequency and schedule of these maneuver campaigns. These have to be resolved through coordination. The A-Train recently completed its Spring 2009 inclination adjust maneuver campaign involving 31 coordinated maneuvers.

4.3 Minimal Coordination of Science Operations

Constellation science operations do not necessarily require a lot of coordination; this depends on the types of measurements the satellites make. For the A-Train, science operations are loosely coordinated since all of the instruments perform observations in accordance with predetermined operational modes during the 16-day repeat cycle. Science teams are able to conduct their day-to-day operations with little or no coordination. For constellations involving more variable targeted observations, more significant interactions would be needed.

One activity that does require coordination is spacecraft maneuvers. Maneuvers are periodically performed to maintain a satellite's orbit requirements, but have the undesirable impact of interrupting science observations. Loss of observation time is unavoidable, but the impact on concurrent science with other constellation instruments can be lessened if the maneuvers are planned to avoid critical observation periods. For example, a team may be participating in a seasonal science campaign and would like to have data sets from other constellation instruments during the campaign. The team advertises its campaign schedule so that if possible, maneuvers for the other satellites can be rescheduled to occur before or after the campaign. In this manner, the amount of coincidental science data for the campaign is maximized.

4.4 Flexibility

A constellation must be both risk-averse and flexible at the same time. The coordination mechanisms must be designed to allow missions to change configurations in response to new requirements. For the A-Train, several changes have been made in response to specific requests from the science teams, for example, the relocation of the Aura satellite to improve overlap with CloudSat. In every case, the goal of

each change has been to improve the science data quality. The primary avenue for communicating and then implementing these changes is the MOWG configuration change-control process. Changes are formally proposed as Change Requests for review, analysis, and comment by all the constellation teams. Once all issues have been discussed and resolved, the changes are approved and implemented.

4.5 Issue Resolution Process

Occasionally, constellation teams may differ on their approaches to constellation operations. A process needs to be established early to provide a clear path to escalate unresolved issues. This was deemed especially important for the A-Train since it involves organizations from more than one space agency and therefore no single, central authority exists. Accordingly, the A-Train MOWG established a procedure that encourages decision-making at the lowest levels, but provides for escalation to NASA Headquarters and CNES Headquarters, if necessary.

4.6 Data Sharing

The primary rationale to form constellations is to maximize the overall science return, so the mission teams involved have to maintain an open data policy, as is done within the A-Train. Science data sharing is facilitated to maximize use of the coincident science data. NASA developed a web-based system known as the A-Train Data Depot (ATDD). The ATDD processes, archives, allows access to, visualizes, analyzes, and correlates distributed atmospheric measurements from A-Train instruments. The ATDD portal provides easy on-line data access and services for science, applications, and educational use so that users get exactly the data that they need [4].

5. CONSTELLATION LIFE CYCLE

Space agencies or constellation “owners” need to take the long view when planning for the establishment, evolution, and retirement of constellations. Space agencies may decide to form new constellations if existing constellations do not meet the science requirements of new/future missions. The key constellation drivers are the science and complementary science observation requirements, which are translated into orbital parameters such as the orbital height, inclination, repeat cycle (if any), and local lighting requirements.

Constellation owners should have a replenishment strategy so that the constellation evolves with the addition of new satellites/instruments and the removal of old or non-functioning ones. Agency management and decision makers need to perform long term planning so that replacement missions are launched sufficiently in advance to ensure continuous, correlated science data over a long time period.

Because of their considerable investments, current constellation teams should be involved in evaluating

proposed additions to the constellation to make the insertion of the new satellites smooth and operations successful. For instance, new satellites must not present unacceptable risks to the existing satellites (e.g., from RFI). In addition, new satellites must have a plan for safe entry into the constellation.

There are several factors to consider when removing a satellite from a constellation. From a safety point of view, it is important to remove a satellite before it presents a danger to other constellation satellites, a situation that occurs once all maneuvering capability has been lost. This can occur at any time during the mission. Understanding why and when a satellite needs to leave is critical to the safety of all the satellites in the same orbit. Constellation teams must also be prepared to handle the case of a member satellite that experiences incapacitating failures. If necessary, the other constellation satellites may have to perform evasive maneuvers in order to avoid collisions.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The benefits of flying constellations are beginning to be appreciated. One of the keys to success is having a constellation infrastructure that enforces guidelines to maximize safety and science returns while minimizing coordination. To satisfy evolving science needs, constellation owners must have a replenishment strategy that provides for the addition of new satellites and the replacement of old or failing satellites, and in some cases, the formation of new constellations. The experiences and successes of the Morning Constellation and the A-Train can be applied to future constellations under consideration.

7. REFERENCES

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